

Studies on Mannich Reaction of 1-Benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines[†]

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The effect of substituents in Mannich cyclisation reaction of 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines has been studied. Both *para*- and *ortho*-cyclisation products are formed when hydroxyl groups are present in the benzene ring of the benzyloxy moiety whereas only *para*-cyclisation product is formed when methoxyl functions are present in it. Further, in the presence of an electron-withdrawing group the hydroxy compounds give only *para*-product and the methoxy compounds instead of yielding the cyclised product give the corresponding *N*-methyl derivatives.

AMONG the several approaches for the synthesis of tetrahydroprotoberberines, the Mannich cyclisation¹⁻³ of 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines with formaldehyde is still the most common and convenient procedure. We had an occasion to employ this reaction during the syntheses of substituted-tetrahydroprotoberberines from the corresponding 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines which we required for 'aberrant biosynthesis' and also for structure-activity relationship. In the present communication we report the syntheses of some substituted-protoberberines from the corresponding 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines by Mannich reaction and also report the effect of substituents in Mannich cyclisation reaction of 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines.

The 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines used in the present study were synthesised by the standard procedure (Scheme 1). Bromination of isovanillin gave 6-bromoisovanillin⁴ (1). Demethylation of 1 with AlCl₃ afforded 2-bromocatechuraldehyde⁵ (2). Benzoylation of 2 gave 2-bromo-4,5-dibenzoyloxybenzaldehyde⁶ (3) which on sodium borohydride reduction furnished the benzyl alcohol (4). 4 was treated with SOCl₂ to give the benzyl chloride (5) which on treatment with KCN afforded 6. Alkaline hydrolysis of 6 gave the bromophenylacetic acid⁷ (7) in 62% yield. Reaction of 7 with SOCl₂ furnished the acid chloride (8). Condensation of 3,4-dimethoxyphenethylamine⁸ (9) in the presence of alkali yielded the amide (10). Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation of 10 in benzene and POCl₃ furnished 3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (11). NaBH₄-reduction of 11 gave 12 which by acid-catalysed hydrogenolysis finally afforded bromo-1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline (13). The substituted-1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines (19, 22, 25 and 28) were similarly prepared from their respective benzyl derivatives⁹⁻¹² (18, 21, 24 and 27).

Scheme 1

Bromine atom has been used to block certain cyclisation sites for directing the cyclisation in

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Mannich reaction on several occasions¹⁵⁻¹⁶ Mannich reaction (Scheme 1) of **13** with HCHO in H₂O afforded (±)-12-bromotetrahydroprotoberberine (**14**) which was characterised by its spectral data. ¹H nmr spectra of **14** had signals for three aromatic protons at δ 6.55, 6.72 and 6.87 (each 1H, s) and 2 methoxyl groups at δ 3.81 and 3.87 (each 3H, s). In the mass spectra of **14**, the molecular ion peak was at 406 (M⁺) and the other prominent fragments were at 326, 192 and 190. Debromination of **14** with lithium aluminium hydride gave the 9,10-dihydroxytetrahydroprotoberberine¹⁷ (**15**). *O*-Methylation of **14** with CH₃N₃ afforded (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine^{17,18} (**16**) which on debromination with Zn/NaOH yielded (±)-tetrahydropalmatine¹⁷ (**17**), an alkaloid isolated previously from many Menispermaceous plants.

Mannich cyclisation reaction (Scheme 1) giving different products under different pH conditions is reported¹⁹⁻²¹. Mannich condensation (Scheme 2) of **19** with HCHO in H₂O gave a mixture of two isomers which were expected to be formed due to *ortho*- and *para*-directing nature of hydroxy group. The ratio of these two isomers was found to be 50 : 50 on silica gel tlc plate. The mixture was

resolved by silica gel preparative tlc. The compounds thus obtained, were characterised as 2,3,9,10- and 2,3,10,11-substituted-tetrahydroprotoberberines²⁰ (**15** and **20**), respectively, on the basis of their ¹H nmr spectral analysis. In isomer **15** the singlet of C₁ and C₄ aromatic protons and doublets of C₁₁ and C₁₃ protons were in the region δ 6.39-6.70. In isomer **20** the signals for 4 aromatic protons were at δ 6.50 (1H), 6.59 (2H) and 6.80 (1H). Both the isomers **15** and **20**, however, had molecular ion peak at 327 (M⁺) in their respective mass spectra, and in both, the other significant ions were at 192, 190, 178, 176 and 136.

Mannich condensation of **19** (Scheme 2) with HCHO in glacial acetic acid as per procedure reported¹⁴ afforded **15** and **20** in the ratio of 10 : 90. Mannich reaction of **22** (Scheme 2) with HCHO in H₂O furnished a single product which was characterised as 2-hydroxy-3,10,11-trimethoxy-tetrahydroprotoberberine (**23**) on the basis of its spectral data. ¹H nmr spectra of **23** had signals for three aromatic methoxyl groups, the signals for four aromatic protons were at δ 6.47 (2H), 6.52 (1H) and 6.70 (1H). Molecular ion peak in the mass spectra of **23** was at 341 (M⁺) and the other prominent fragments were at 326, 178, 164 and 149. The identity of **23** with naturally occurring alkaloid, govanine¹⁰ was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Treatment of the bromo-1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline (**25**) with HCHO in H₂O under Mannich condition²¹ yielded *N*-methyl derivative (**26**) instead of the corresponding tetrahydroprotoberberine. The compound **26** was characterised by its spectra data. ¹H nmr spectra (60 MHz) of **26** had signals for *N*-CH₃ group at δ 2.38, 3.63 (2 × O-CH₃), 3.78 (1 × O-CH₃) and four aromatic protons at δ 6.24 (1H), 6.49 (2H) and 6.90 (1H). Other data of the compound were also in complete agreement with that of **26** reported in literature²².

Mannich condensation of **28** with HCHO in H₂O afforded (±)-12-nitrocoreximine^{1,2} (**29**). ¹H nmr spectra of **29** had signals for three aromatic protons at δ 6.42 (1H), 6.55 (1H) and 6.58 (1H) as singlets and for two methoxyl groups (2 × O-CH₃) at 3.69. The molecular ion peak in the mass spectra of **29** was at 372 (M⁺) and the other fragment ions were at 355, 342, 178 and 176. Treatment of the nitro compound (**28**) with HCHO in glacial AcOH gave the corresponding *N*-methyl derivative (**30**) as the major product. In ¹H nmr spectra of **30** a singlet at δ 2.21 was for *N*-CH₃ and signals for four aromatic protons were at δ 6.20, 6.32 (each singlet) and 6.51 and 6.62 (each doublet, *J* 9.5 Hz, two *ortho*-coupled protons).

The ir, uv, ¹H nmr and mass spectra and elemental analyses of the compounds were in complete agreement with the assigned structures.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in a H₂SO₄-bath and are uncorrected. The compounds were routinely

Scheme 2

checked by tlc and ir, ^1H nmr and mass spectra for purity and confirmation of the assigned structure. All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

2-Bromo-4,5-dibenzyloxybenzaldehyde (3) : A mixture of 2-bromo-4,5-dihydroxybenzaldehyde⁵ (2; 10 g) prepared from 2-bromo-5-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde⁴ (1), K_2CO_3 (10 g), NaI (250 mg), EtOH (150 ml) and benzyl chloride (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure, the residue extracted with CHCl_3 , washed with aqueous 30% NaOH (2 × 25 ml), water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated to give 3 (12 g, 66%), m.p. 95–6° (hexane) (Found: C, 63.2; H, 4.1. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrO}_3$ requires: C, 63.5; H, 4.3%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 665 cm^{-1} (CHO); δ (CDCl_3) 5.05, 5.09 (each 4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 7.02 (1H, s, ArH), 7.30 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 7.44 (1H, s, ArH), 10.06 (1H, s, OH).

2-Bromo-4,5-dibenzyloxybenzyl alcohol (4) : To an ice-cold stirred solution of 3 (10 g) in MeOH (450 ml), NaBH_4 (3.5 g) was added in portions and the stirring continued for 2 h at ambient temperature. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure, the residue treated with water (100 ml), extracted with CHCl_3 , washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to give 4 (8.6 g, 86%), m.p. 92–3° (benzene–hexane) (Found: C, 62.8; H, 4.9. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrO}_3$ requires: C, 63.2; H, 4.8%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 cm^{-1} (OH); δ (CDCl_3) 4.38 (2H, s, CH_2OH), 4.90 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.90 (2H, s, ArH), 7.20 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$).

2-Bromo-4,5-dibenzyloxybenzyl chloride (5) : To an ice-cold stirred solution of 4 (8 g) in dry ether (100 ml), SOCl_2 (11 ml) was added dropwise and the stirring continued at ambient temperature for 5 h. The excess of solvent and the reagent were removed under reduced pressure to give 5 (6.5 g, 81%), m.p. 100–01° (benzene–hexane); δ (CDCl_3) 4.51 (2H, s, CH_2Cl), 5.03 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.98, 7.03 (each 2H, s, ArH), 7.30 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$).

2-Bromo-4,5-dibenzyloxybenzyl nitrile (6) : To a stirred suspension of KCN (4 g) in dry DMSO (50 ml), a solution of 5 (6 g) in DMSO (150 ml) was added slowly and the stirring continued for 30 h at room temperature. Water (450 ml) was added to the resulting mixture, extracted with CHCl_3 , washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to afford 6 (4.2 g, 70%), m.p. 74–5° (benzene–hexane) (Found: C, 64.3; H, 4.5; N, 3.3. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrNO}_2$ requires: C, 64.7; H, 4.4; N, 3.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 230 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$); δ (CDCl_3) 3.59 (2H, s, CH_2CN), 5.00, 5.20 (each 4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.98, 7.20 (each 2H, s, ArH) and 7.30 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$).

2-Bromo-4,5-dibenzyloxyphenylacetic acid (7) : A mixture of 6 (4 g), $(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_2$ (80 ml) and aqueous KOH (25%, 40 ml) was heated under reflux for 20 h. Water (120 ml) was added to the cooled mixture, extracted with CHCl_3 and extract discarded. The

aqueous layer was acidified with 10% HCl, extracted with EtOAc, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to give 7 (2.6 g, 62%), m.p. 135–37° (ether–hexane) (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.6. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrO}_4$ requires: C, 61.8; H, 4.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 900 (OH) and 1 690 cm^{-1} (CO); δ (acetone- d_6) 3.52 (2H, s, CH_2COOH), 4.99, 5.03 (each 4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 7.05, 7.10 (each 2H, s, ArH) and 7.12–7.52 (10H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$).

2-Bromo-4,5-dibenzyloxyphenylacetyl chloride (8) : To a stirred solution of 7 (5 g) in dry C_6H_6 (30 ml), SOCl_2 (8 ml) was added and heated under reflux for 3.5 h. The excess solvent and reagent were removed under reduced pressure to give 8 which was used without further purification, δ (CDCl_3) 4.08 (2H, s, CH_2COCl), 5.02 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.75, 7.08 (each 2H, s, ArH) and 7.30 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$).

N-[3,4-Dimethoxyphenethyl]-4',5'-dibenzyloxy-2'-bromophenylacetamide (10) : To a stirred mixture of 3,4-dimethoxyphenethylamine⁹ (9; 3 g) in C_6H_6 (20 ml) and 4N NaOH (80 ml), a solution of 8 (4.5 g) in dry C_6H_6 (400 ml) was slowly added and the stirring continued for 4 h at room temperature. The benzene layer was then separated, washed with 1N HCl, water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to give 10 (5.1 g, 72%), m.p. 148–49° (ether–hexane) (Found: C, 64.8; H, 5.2; N, 2.3. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{32}\text{BrNO}_6$ requires: C, 65.1; H, 5.4; N, 2.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 320 (NH) and 1 630 cm^{-1} (CO); δ (CDCl_3) 2.59 (2H, t, J 6.5 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}$), 3.30 (2H, t, J 6.5 Hz, CH_2NHCO), 3.45 (2H, s, NHCOCH_2), 3.72, 3.76 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 5.00, 5.03 (each 4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.40–7.10 (5H, m, ArH) and 7.31 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$); m/z 590 (M^+).

1-[2'-Bromo-4',5'-dibenzyloxybenzyl]-6,7-dimethoxy-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (11) : A mixture of 10 (5 g), dry C_6H_6 (100 ml) and freshly distilled POCl_3 (12 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 2.5 h. The excess of solvent and reagent were removed under reduced pressure to give 11.HCl (3.4 g, 68%), m.p. 177–78° (MeOH–ether); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 630 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$); 11 free base δ (CDCl_3) 3.68, 3.80 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.97 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.53 (1H, s, ArH), 6.81 (2H, s, ArH), 7.00 (1H, s, ArH) and 7.06–7.30 (10H, m, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$).

1-[2'-Bromo-4',5'-dibenzyloxybenzyl]-6,7-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (12) : To an ice-cooled stirred solution of 11.HCl (5 g) in MeOH (200 ml), NaBH_4 (2.4 g) was added in portions and the stirring continued for 2 h at ambient temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was extracted with CHCl_3 , washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to give 12 (2.4 g, 51%), m.p. 110–11° (ether–hexane) (Found: C, 66.4; H, 6.0; N, 2.3. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{34}\text{BrNO}_4$ requires: C, 66.9; H, 5.6; N, 2.4%); δ (CDCl_3) 3.71, 3.77 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 5.03 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.50, 6.62,

6.73, 7.08 (each 4H, s, ArH) and 7.30 (10H, bs, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$).

1-[2'-Bromo-4',5'-dihydroxybenzyl]-6,7-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (13): A mixture of **12** (2 g), EtOH (50 ml) and 12 N HCl (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 h. The excess solvent and reagent were removed under reduced pressure to give **13.HCl** (1.1 g, 74%), m.p. 140–42° (MeOH–ether) (Found: C, 50.3; H, 4.5, N, 3.0. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{BrNO}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: C, 50.2; H, 4.9; N, 3.3%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 cm^{-1} (OH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.70 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.60, 6.65, 6.70 and 6.99 (each 4H, s, ArH).

Mannich reaction of 13: A mixture of **13.HCl** (1 g), 37% HCHO (25 ml) and H_2O (25 ml) was heated at 100° for 4 h. The excess solvent and reagent were removed under reduced pressure, the residue basified with 28% NH_3 solution, extracted with EtOAc, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) the solvent removed to give 2,3-dimethoxy-9,10-dihydroxy-5,8,13,13a-tetrahydro-12-bromo-6H-dibenzo [a,g]quinolizine (**14**; 640 mg, 68%), m.p. 120–22° (ether–hexane) (Found: C, 55.8; H, 5.0; N, 3.2. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{BrNO}_4$ requires: C, 56.2; H, 4.9; N, 3.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH) and 2 700–2 815 cm^{-1} (*trans*-quinolizidine); δ (CDCl_3) 3.81, 3.84 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.55, 6.72 and 6.87 (each 3H, s, ArH); m/z 406 (M^+), 326, 192 and 190.

Debromination of 14: To a stirred suspension of LiAlH_4 (350 mg) in THF (15 ml), a solution of **14** (250 mg) in THF (12 ml) was added dropwise and the mixture heated at 55° for 4 h. The excess LiAlH_4 was decomposed by dropwise addition of EtOAc followed by water and the organic layer decanted. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give a residue, which was extracted with EtOAc, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to give a solid, purified as hydrochloride (120 mg, 55%). It resembled to **15**, obtained during the Mannich reaction of **19**.

O-Methylation of 14: To a solution of **14** (250 mg) in THF (20 ml) and MeOH (7 ml), an excess ethereal solution of CH_3N_3 was added and the mixture set aside at room temperature for 48 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue extracted with CHCl_3 , washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to give (\pm)-12-bromotetrahydropalmitine (**16**; 160 mg, 60%), m.p. 160–61° (lit.⁸, 162°).

(\pm)-**Tetrahydropalmitine (17):** A mixture of **16** (100 mg), EtOH (10 ml), 40% aqueous NaOH (1 ml) and Zn dust (90 mg) was heated under reflux for 2 h and the solution filtered. The filtrate was concentrated, the residue extracted with CHCl_3 , washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to give **17** (50 mg, 61%), m.p. 150–51° (lit.⁸, 151°).

1-[3',4'-Dihydroxybenzyl]-6,7-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (19): It was prepared from the dibenzyl derivative⁷ (**18**) as **19.HCl** by the procedure as described for **13**, (73%), m.p. 242–

44°d (MeOH–ether) (Found: C, 61.3; H, 6.6; N, 4.1. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: C, 61.5; H, 6.3; N, 4.0%) ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 cm^{-1} (OH); δ (acetone- d_6) 3.62, 3.65 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$) and 6.35–6.80 (5H, m, ArH).

Mannich reaction of 19: [A] Mannich reaction of **19.HCl** using the reaction conditions as described in case of **13**, yielded a mixture of two isomers **15** and **20** which were purified by preparative tlc plates (silica gel; solvent: CHCl_3 –MeOH, 94:6). The major bands on the plates were cut out, eluted with a mixture of CHCl_3 –MeOH (3:1) and purified as their hydrochlorides: The isomer **15.HCl** (29%), m.p. 230–32° (MeOH–ether) (Found: C, 62.3; H, 6.2; N, 3.5. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: C, 62.7; H, 6.1; N, 3.9%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 cm^{-1} (OH); λ_{max} (MeOH) 284 nm, (MeOH+NaOH) 290 and 395 nm; **15** free base δ (CDCl_3) 3.82, 3.83 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$) and 6.39–6.70 (4H, m, ArH); m/z 327 (M^+), 326 (M^+-1), 192, 190, 178, 176 and 136; The isomer **20.HCl** (27%), m.p. 214–15° (MeOH–ether) (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.9; N, 3.6. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: C, 62.7; H, 6.1; N, 3.9%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 cm^{-1} (OH); λ_{max} (MeOH) 287 nm, (MeOH+NaOH) 292 and 335 nm; **20** free base δ (acetone- d_6) 3.70, 3.72 (each 6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.50 (1H, s, ArH), 6.59 (2H, s, ArH) and 6.80 (1H, s, ArH); m/z 327 (M^+), 326 (M^+-1), 192, 190, 178, 176 and 136. [B] A mixture of **19.HCl** (1 g), glacial AcOH (10 ml) and 37% HCHO (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 h. The resulting mixture was basified with 28% NH_3 solution, extracted with EtOAc, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to afford **20** as a major isomer.

1-[3',4'-Dimethoxybenzyl]-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (22): It was prepared from the benzyl derivative⁸ (**21**) as **22.HCl** by the procedure as described for **13**, (78%), m.p. 259–60° (MeOH–ether) (Found: C, 61.9; H, 6.6; N, 3.4. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: C, 62.4; H, 6.6; N, 3.8%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 cm^{-1} (OH); **22** free base δ (CDCl_3) 3.68, 3.71, 3.76 (each 9H, s, $3 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.43 (1H, s, ArH) and 6.68 (4H, s, ArH).

Mannich reaction of 22: Mannich reaction of **22.HCl** as described in case of **13** afforded **23**, (52%), m.p. 167–68° (ether–hexane) (lit.¹⁰ 168–70°); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 cm^{-1} (OH); δ (CDCl_3) 3.72 (9H, s, $3 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.47 (2H, s, ArH), 6.52 and 6.70 (each 2H, s, ArH); m/z 341 (M^+), 340 (M^+-1), 326, 178, 176, 164 and 149.

1-[2'-Bromo-4',5'-dimethoxy]-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (25): It was prepared from the benzyl derivative¹¹ (**24**) as **25.HCl** by the procedure as described for **13**, (74%), m.p. 285–87° (MeOH–ether); **25** free base m.p. 134–35° (ether–hexane) (Found: C, 51.4; H, 5.0; N, 3.2. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{BrNO}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: C, 51.3; H, 5.2; N, 3.1%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 cm^{-1} (OH); δ (CDCl_3) 3.72 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.44, 6.68, 6.75, 6.91 (each 4H, s, ArH).

Mannich reaction of 25: A mixture of 25.HCl (200 mg), H₂O (5 ml) and 37% HCHO (5 ml) was heated for 4 h at 100° and worked up as usual to afford a solid which was purified by preparative tlc plates (silica gel; solvent: CHCl₃-MeOH, 96:4). The major band on the plates was cut out and eluted with a mixture of CHCl₃-MeOH (4:1) to give 26, purified as 26.HCl (140 mg, 77%), m.p. 145-46° (MeOH-ether) (lit.²² 148-50°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH); 26 free base δ (CDCl₃; 60 MHz) 2.38 (3H, s, NCH₃), 3.63 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.78 (6H, s, 2×OCH₃), 6.24 (1H, s, ArH), 6.49 (2H, s, ArH) and 6.90 (1H, s, ArH).

1 - [3' - Hydroxy-4'-methoxy-2'-nitrobenzyl] - 7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (28): It was prepared from the dibenzyl derivative¹² (27) as 28.HCl by the method as described for 13, (67%), m.p. 190-92°d (MeOH-ether), and the other data cited in our previous communication¹².

Mannich reaction of 28: [A] A mixture of 28 HCl (1 g), 37% HCHO (25 ml) and H₂O (25 ml) was heated for 4 h at 100°. The excess solvent and reagent were removed under reduced pressure to give a solid which was treated with hot MeOH (4×15 ml) and filtered. The removal of solvent from the filtrate gave (±)-12-nitrocoreximine (29), purified as 19.HCl (620 mg, 65%), m.p. 250° (MeOH-ether), and the other data cited in our previous communication¹².

[B] The above reaction of 28.HCl in glacial AcOH and 37% HCHO at 130° for 2 h gave 30, purified as 30.HCl (70%), m.p. 159-60° (MeOH-ether) (Found: C, 55.5; H, 5.7; N, 6.4. C₁₉H₂₂N₂O₆.HCl requires: C, 55.6; H, 5.6; N, 6.8%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 525 and 1 360 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); 30.HCl δ (CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) 2.21 (3H, s, NCH₃), 3.67, 3.69 (each 6H, s, 2×OCH₃),

6.20, 6.32 (each 2H, s, ArH), 6.51 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArH), 6.65 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArH).

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